

CHARACTERIZATION OF BACTERIAL CENOSES INHABITING SOILS OF URBAN TERRITORIES

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Annotation. Soil samples of urban territories were analyzed. It was found that anthropogenic pressure resulted in decreased biodiversity of studied soil microbiota. Microbial species suitable for bioindication of technogenic contamination and for further experiments were represented by *Azotobacter* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Escherichia* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Rhodococcus* sp., *Streptomyces* sp.

Key words: bacteria, soil, monitoring, microbiology.

Аннотация. Проанализированы образцы почв городских территорий. Установлено, что под воздействием антропогенной нагрузки снижается биоразнообразие почвенной микробиоты исследуемых почв. В качестве микроорганизмов, пригодных для биоиндикации техногенных загрязнений и для дальнейшей работы отобраны *Azotobacter* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Escherichia* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Rhodococcus* sp., *Streptomyces* sp.

Ключевые слова: бактерии, почва, мониторинг, микробиология.

Annotatsiya. Shaharlarning ko'p funksiyali hududlaridan olingan tuproq namunalari tahlil qilindi. Tadqiq qilingan tuproqlarda antropogen bosim ta'sirida tuproq mikrobiotasining biologik xilma-xilligi kamayib borishi aniqlandi. Texnogen ifloslanishlarni bioindikatsiya qilish va keyingi ishlar uchun mos mikroorganizmlar sifatida *Azotobacter* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Escherichia* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Rhodococcus* sp., *Streptomyces* sp. turlari tanlab olingan.

Kalit so'zlar: bakteriyalar, tuproq, monitoring, mikrobiologiya.

Introduction. The soils of urban territories are unique and complex ecosystems exposed to impact of numerous stress factors significantly deteriorating their quality. In urban soils diverse adverse processes take place due to disruption and degradation of soil profile, dehumification, overcondensation, disbalance of aquatic-aerial, thermal, alimentary and gas regimes, chemical and biological pollution, preservation of biodiversity [1].

Rain water dissolves and transfers the pollutants from the air of municipal enterprises, including volatile organic compounds and precipitates them on soil surface [2]. Transport is a source of contamination of urban soil due to discharges of volatile compounds and solid particles [3]. The materials serving as traffic coating may act as reservoirs for the pollutants such as heavy metal and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons [4].

Soils are natural accumulators of heavy metals in the environment and the main source of contamination of adjacent media, including plants [4, 5]. Getting in to soil, heavy metal are engaged in all occurring processes, are involved in all principal functions and are implicated in all major migration cycles taking place in biosphere [1]. Rising technogenic pressure on the environment leads to emergence within the municipal line of zones with critical ecological

situation. Such challenges require constant complex ecological monitoring, to conduct investigations allowing to detect and evaluate contamination hazards, to reveal trends and rate of developments [1].

Microorganisms to a large extent are responsible for environmental conditions, some microbial populations rapidly respond to change in the environment and they may be utilized to assess the quality of the environment to meet our requirements.

Soil microorganisms are capable to decompose several toxic agents, transforms them to less hazardous forms. Anthropogenic modification of soils from municipal territories results in degradation of humus soil layer which is often the habitat for soil microorganisms. Reducing the depth of humus soil layer effects soil quality, turning fertile soils into less productive lands with the prevalence of oligotrophic microbial species. Also, conditions of technogenic soil contamination (the supply of elevated doses of fertilizers, excess of pesticides and heavy metals) leads to accumulation of toxigenic microbial species [6].

Bacteria are part of invisible biodiversity surrounding us and even inhabiting us. Microbial cenoses of urban soils are extremely significant for biogeochemical transformation of municipal wastes, are the crucial factors determining the dynamics of organic matter in soil and playing the beneficial role to withstand anthropogenic pressure [7, 8].

Investigation of make-up of bacterial cenoses in soils of urban territories will enable to analyze the adaptive mechanisms of microorganisms to changing conditions of the environment.

Aim of study – investigation of composition of bacterial cenoses of urban territories exposed to diverse types of contamination.

Materials and methods. Soil samples were used taken in the direct vicinity to the A-100 gas station in Minsk, Minsk Heating Equipment Plant, Minsk Car Ring Road, and Belgazconstruction plant distinguished by different levels of anthropogenic pressure. The samples were taken from the depth approximately 10 cm.

Isolation and determination of the number of microorganisms in soil samples were performed by seeding aqueous suspension on meat-peptone agar (MPA). The culture was carried out at temperatures of 20-37 °C during 7 days with a daily counting of grown colonies.

Isolated colonies were grown on MPA until monocultures were produced. The analysis, purity of the cultures, identification were carried out visually and microscopically.

Results and discussion. It was found the conducted investigations that soil microbiota is represented by 7 genera belonging to 6 families: *Pseudomonadaceae* (*Azotobacter* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp.), *Micrococcaceae* (*Arthrobacter* sp.), *Streptomycetaceae* (*Streptomyces* sp.), *Nocardiaceae* (*Rhodococcus* sp.), *Enterobacteriaceae* (*Escherichia* sp.), and *Bacillaceae* (*Bacillus* sp.) (Figure). This indicates that anthropogenic pressure reduces the biodiversity soil microbiota in the studied soils.

a

б

a – gram-positive rods; б – gram-positive cocci

Figure. Cell morphology of certain isolates under light microscope, is magnified by 1000 times

It should be also noted that the this analyzed soil samples the number of bacteria has been reduced ($1,2 \times 10^5$ – $7,0 \times 10^6$ CFU/g dry. soil). The highest amount of microorganisms was detected around Belgazconstruction plant ($7,0 \times 10^6$ CFU/g dry. soil), and the minimum amount was found around Minsk Heating Equipment Plant ($1,2 \times 10^5$ CFU/g dry. soil).

In the samples taken around Minsk Car Ring Road and Minsk Heating Equipment Plant species *Azotobacter* and *Rhodococcus* prevailed. This is determined by the fact that bacteria of genus *Azotobacter* are capable to grow on media with high level of sodium chloride and other salts widely applied in winter period as an anti-icing agent for the treatment of road surfaces. Bacteria *Rhodococcus* are capable to utilize oil and its derivatives, the amount of which exceeds the normal values in the tested soils samples.

As to soil samples collected from the areas lying in direct vicinity to Belgazconstruction plant, they are dominated by *Bacillus* sp. Bacteria of genus *Bacillus* prevail in urban soils due to increased sporulation capacity, elevated resistance to adverse media factors and diminished competitive potential of more sensitive to urbanization species. They may be regarded as species indicative to heavy metal contamination, as it is known that increased population of sporulation bacteria testifies to the growing concentration in soil of heavy metal, especially lead, cadmium, and copper.

Conclusion. Summing up, it was found as the result of performed studies that under the impact of anthropogenic pressure the biodiversity of soil microbiota in the examined samples tends to fall. Soil microbiota of the studied areas is represented by 7 bacterial genera belonging to 6 families. It enabled to select microorganisms suitable for bioindication of technogenic contamination and for further experiments representatives of species *Azotobacter* sp., *Bacillus* sp., *Escherichia* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., *Rhodococcus* sp., *Streptomyces* sp.

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REFERENCES

1. Soils and technogenic surface formations in urban landscapes: A monograph / G.V. Kovaleva [et al.] – Vladivostok: Dalnauka Publishing House, 2012. – 159 p.
2. Scavenging effect of precipitation on volatile organic compounds in ambient atmosphere / E. Sato [et al.] // Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn. – Vol. 79. – 2006. – P. 1231–1233.
3. Correlation between microbial communities and volatile organic compounds in an urban soil provides clues on soil quality towards sustainability of city flowerbeds / F. Sillo [et al.] // Vol. 10, Issue 1. – 2024. – <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e23594>.
4. Impervious surfaces alter soil bacterial communities in urban areas: a case study 430 in Beijing, China / Y. Hu [et al.] // Front. Microbiol. – 2018. – Vol. 9. – P. 226.
5. Effect of soil sealing on the microbial biomass, N transformation and related enzyme activities at various depths of soils in urban area of Beijing, China / D. Zhao [et al.] // J. Soils Sediments. – 2012. – Vol. 500, 12 (4). – P. 519-530.
6. Zhurlov, O.S. Methodological approaches to the study of microbial communities degraded soils of urbanized territories / O.S. Zhurlov, A.A. Mushinskiy // [Electronic

- resource]. – Режим доступа: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/methodological-approaches-to-the-study-of-microbial-communities-degraded-soils-of-urbanized-territories/viewer>. – Дата доступа: 09.07.2025.
7. Soil Microbial Communities in Urban Environment October 2020. *Advances in Environmental Research*. – Publisher: Nova Science Publisher, USA. – Vol. 76. / A. Gorovtsov [et al.] // [Electronic resource]. – Режим доступа: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344608820_Soil_Microbial_Communities_in_Urban_Environment. – Дата доступа: 09.07.2025.
 8. Different response of bacterial community to the changes of nutrients and pollutants in sediments from an urban river network / F. Zhang [et al.] // *Frontiers of Environmental Science & Engineering*. – 2020. – Vol. 14. – P. 28.